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IMPACT OF DEMONETIZATION ON FMCG SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

This paper is about the high impact jolt, the FMCG sector face during the Demonetization drive initiated by our hon'ble PM Narendra Modi on the 8th November, 2016. FMCG sector is one of the most leading sectors in India-Rural or Punjab. To control parallel economy, the drive was initiated as a result there was a ban on notes of Rs500 & Rs1000 denomination as a legal tender. The Indian Economy faced a huge cash crunch. Going cashless, the population did not have money to buy their daily need goods. The stores had stopped accepting the banned currency and the new currency was hardly in circulation. This paper shows the percentage drop in sales of FMCG goods and the supplies as well. The supplies were affected, the suppliers were affected, the consumers were affected and even the transporters were affected. There was hardly any possibility to store the new stock as the existing stock still existed in the stores.

Keywords: Demonetization, Cash Crunch, FMCG, Parallel Economy

Introduction: It's a known fact that The fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) segment is the fourth largest sector in the Indian economy. The market size of FMCG in India is estimated to grow from US\$ 30 billion in 2011 to US\$ 74 billion in 2018. Food products(bread, butter, milk etc) is the leading segment, accounting for 43 per cent of the overall market. Personal care(Soap, shampoo) accounts for 22 per cent and fabric care (12 per cent) come next in terms of market share.

Growing awareness, easier access, dual- working couples and changing lifestyles have been the key growth drivers for this sector.

This paper talks about the impact on this very important sector after the note ban. Public was suddenly left cashless right from 8 PM onwards on the 8th November, 2016, when PM Narendra Modi Announced his new move to cut shadow economy-demonetization. It was not just the urban sector which faced the brunt of demonetization; the rural sector faced it too. In fact, its majorly the rural sector which has almost negligible amount in the banks and more in their pockets. Demonetization has created a vicious circle of cash crunch during the last quarter as right from the dealers, to transporters, to producers and the buyers. Not just shopping from the stores had dropped immediately, but online shopping of FMCG too had seen a drastic decline in the sales. Almost Rs2.6 trillion packed goods industry mostly transact in cash.

S&P BSE Fast Moving Consumer Goods index declined almost 6% after demonetization.

Demonetization: Demonetization is the act of stripping a currency unit of its status as legal tender. Demonetization is necessary where a change of national currency is needed. The old unit of currency must be retired and replaced with a new currency unit.

There are multiple reasons why nations demonetize their local units of currency. Some reasons include to combat inflation, to combat corruption, to combat parallel economy and to discourage a cash system. The

process of demonetization involves either introducing new notes or coins of the same currency or completely replacing the old currency with new currency.

On 8th November 2016, the Indian government announced the demonetization of the 500- and 1000- rupee notes, the two biggest denomination notes. These notes accounted for 86% of the India's cash supply. The government's goal was to eradicate counterfeit currency, fight tax evasion, eliminate black money gotten from money laundering and terrorist financing activities, and promote a cashless economy. By making the larger denomination notes worthless, individuals and entities with huge sums of black money gotten from parallel cash systems were forced to exchange the money at a bank which is by law required to acquire tax information from the entity. If the entity could not provide proof of making any tax payments on the cash, a tax penalty of 200% of the tax owed was imposed.

What are FMCG goods?

FMCG(Fast Moving Consumer Goods) is also known as consumer packaged goods. Items in this category include all consumables (other than groceries/pulses) people buy at regular intervals. The most common in the list are toilet soaps, detergents, shampoos, toothpaste, shaving products, shoe polish, packaged foodstuff, and household accessories and extends to certain electronic goods (cells). These items are meant for daily or frequent consumption and have a high return. Their shelf life is low and daily usability is high. FMCG is a compulsory purchase without which the day to day activities of normal household activities are dependent on. A typical FMCG sector has the following characteristics:

1. From the consumers' perspective

- Frequent purchase
- Low involvement (little or no effort to choose the item)
- Low price
- Short shelf life
- Must use for daily consumption

2. From the marketers' angle

- High volumes
- Low contribution margins
- Extensive distribution networks
- High stock turnover

Rural Trends

Rural areas expected to be the major driver for FMCG, as growth continues to be high in these regions. Rural areas saw a 16 per cent, as against 12 per cent rise in urban areas. Most companies rushed to capitalise on this, as they quickly went about increasing direct distribution and providing better infrastructure. Companies are also working towards creating specific products specially targeted for the rural market. The FMCG goods here are not made available in a setup like that of a super market or a hyper store but local karyana stores where credit facility is easily available on the basis of a customer's goodwill. However, there is not huge variety in brands available unlike in the urban sector. Local brands are still prevalent which in the urban sector have been replaced by today's brands.

The Government of India has also been supporting the rural population with higher minimum support prices (MSPs), loan waivers, and disbursements through the National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (NREGA) programme. These measures have helped in reducing poverty in rural India and given a boost to rural purchasing power. There is better brand awareness now. Hence rural demand is set to rise with rising incomes and greater awareness of brands.

Urban trends

With rise in purchasing power, mid- and high-income consumers in urban areas have shifted their purchasing trend from essential to premium products. In response, firms have started enhancing their premium products portfolio. Indian and multinational FMCG players are leveraging India as a strategic sourcing hub for cost-competitive product development and manufacturing to cater to international markets.

Top Companies of FMCG

According to a study conducted by AC Nielsen, 62 of the top 100 brands are owned by MNCs, and the balance by Indian companies. Fifteen companies own these 62 brands, and 27 of these are owned by Hindustan Unilever ltd.

The top ten India FMCG brands are:

1. Hindustan Unilever Ltd.
2. ITC (Indian Tobacco Company)
3. Nestlé India
4. GCFMMF (AMUL)
5. Dabur India
6. Asian Paints (India)
7. Cadbury India
8. Britannia Industries
9. Procter & Gamble Hygiene and Health Care
10. Marico Industries

What the millenniums expect

According to a study by TMW and Marketing Sciences that surveyed 2,000 people across different Demography found that the age groups ranging, young consumers are the most 'rational' and likely to spend more time weighing up potential purchases. The survey also suggests that younger people are using recommendations from their peers and respective reference groups about products and services in order to make rational purchase decisions. According to the study, shoppers aged 18 to 24 are 174 per cent more likely to be impacted from social media than shoppers aged 25 and over.

Another key factor today is – speed. Today's consumer wants packaged goods that work better, faster, and smarter. The “ need for speed” trend highlights the importance of speed as a potentially decisive purchase factor for packaged goods products in a world where distinctions between products are shrinking.

Younger consumers, commonly known as the smart phone generation expresses the greatest need for speed. Datamonitor's 2013 Consumer Survey found that younger consumers those in the 15-24 year old age group were twice as likely to say that "results are achieved quickly" has a "very high amount of influence" on their health and beauty product choices than consumers in the oldest age group, those aged 65 or older.

Impact of Demonetization on FMCG sector

In FMCG Industry, more than 80-85% transactions between retailers to distributors are cash based. Further though most of the large FMCG companies do not extend credit to distributors, but distributors tend to extend credit to retailers typically for a period ranging between 7 days to 3 weeks. Under-reporting of sale at retailer level and transactions without bill by distributors is a rampant practice in trade and is something ignored by FMCG players being off book. All this money which used to typically find its way back in circulation has been made redundant by the governments move. The money which is genuine was also stuck since majority of it is in denominations of Rs 500 or Rs 1000 and the process of conversion is tedious and with a limit of Rs 4000 per day. These transactions being high value in nature was seen taking time before the order is re-established.

The impact of the government's move to eliminate parallel economy on FMCG (fast moving consumer goods) companies can be seen in two parts. One is on the distribution channel as small retailers—who make up the bulk of sales—mostly deal in cash. While consumers will recover relatively quickly as soon as the new currency notes become available, trade channels may take a few weeks as their transactions will be of higher value. If their purchases decline, that will affect sales growth reported by companies.

The second impact is at the consumer level, facing the liquidity crunch. Consumers have been making purchases based on higher priority needs and zero on needs which now sounded them trivial to them. The last quarter, therefore, showed some impact of this development on sales growth of companies. If the rural economy revives as expected, then the headwinds from the government's move will be easier to manage. Even otherwise, it does not appear as if FMCG companies will face any lasting impact because of this decision. Even then, the BSE FMCG index was down by 2.1%. In the Macro Data released on the 13th of January, 2017, it was that the retail inflation fell to 3.41%.

Vegetable markets, departmental stores, milk booths were found empty for many days. As a result, products with very short shelf life were almost expired for usage, resulting in a loss again. Almost Rs2.6 trillion packed goods industry mostly transact in cash at the lower level of supply chain. And more than nine million retailers in India are Kirana store who deals in cash. Since the rural economy is mainly cash based and wholesaler dependent, this shortage of cash has led to slow down in rural sales and demand. Consumers don't have cash. Moreover, paucity of cash has jammed the movement of trucks. Most of the stocks of Consumer durables, consumer non-durables, Food and beverages settled on red in the last quarter.

S&P BSE Fast Moving Consumer Goods index declined almost 6% from November 8, 2016, to December 8, 2016. In food processing companies **ADF food Industries** declined almost 13%, **Britannia** declined almost 6%, **Nestle** declined almost 2%. In beverage and distilleries **United beverages** declined almost 5.2%, **United Spirits** declined almost 4.2% in the same period.

Personal care companies like **Dabur India**, **Colgate**, **Emami** also dipped in the last quarter. Domestic appliances companies like Bajaj Electric and Hawkins too faced the dip.

The Managing Director of Godrej Consumer Products Ltd (GCPL), Mr Vivek Gambhir said . “Given the good monsoon this year, rural sales had begun picking up post harvest from October onwards. This has, however, been significantly impacted in the last quarter due to demonetization.” However, GCPL said that it has been able to perform better than the industry.

Godrej Consumer Products Ltd's India business reported good sales growth as its household insecticides business offset a weak performance in soaps.

The BSE FMCG (fast-moving consumer goods) Index has declined 7.4% since 8 November, the day demonetisation was announced, but has recovered.

The September quarter saw Hindustan Unilever Ltd’s sales volume decline 1%, as an increase in soap prices and withdrawal of promotions led to a decline in volumes. Oral care continued to disappoint, but others such as skin care, hair care and cosmetics did well. Companies have scaled back promotions and even advertising spending, which should also contribute to better profit growth.

Impact of Demonetization on FMCG Industry (Impulse Products): Distributors for Impulse products like beverage and chocolates are usually non –exclusive. This would mean that for a distributor with lower liquidity his preference might force him to divert his limited cash to products which have a high throughput and turnover ratio i.e. either consumer staples or personal care.

An estimate by financial services company Edelweiss has pegged the initial impact of demonetization on nationwide FMCG sales at 20-40%. Impulse categories such as biscuits and salty snacks have taken the biggest hit, along with personal care categories like toilet soaps, shampoos and detergents.

"India had a good sowing season, a good monsoon. There is a rise in the water table. The FMCG sector was starting to come back," said a top executive at one of the country's largest FMCG companies. "Around 45% of FMCG sales happen through the wholesale channel," said Arvind Mediratta, MD & CEO of Metro Cash & Carry India. "And that channel is the worst affected."

For Beverage Industry small restaurants typically contribute ~5% to sales. Packaged Drinking Water and Carbonated soft drinks are the largest selling items (amongst packaged goods) in small restaurants. As per the National Restaurants Association of India, Consumer spends at restaurants have dropped as much as 40% post the demonetization announcement, a clear indication of discretionary spends getting impacted by liquidity crunch. Many patrons have reported to accommodating bottled water as choice of beverage accompanying food rather than the regular carbonated soft drink or fruit drinks. There has been a mixed reaction from trader’s community to the demonetization scheme. While FICCI and Confederation of All India Traders (CAIT) have supported the initiative several state level unions have been very vocal about their dissatisfaction and the negative impact this will have on their business. The good thing which is expected to come out of this is the greater acceptance of digital payments systems which eventually will reduce cost of doing business at all levels (Manufacturer to Retailer). Retail chains such as Big Bazaar and Godrej Nature's Basket saw the biggest upswing due to the availability of card machines in their stores during the demonetization period. Value growth here surged by 21% compared to the corresponding period a year ago. We may now look forward to a world where toffees and candies will no longer be a replacement for petty change in India.

Paytm has been declared an official bank for wallet money. People who could never imagine transacting online or using mobile wallets are now making extensive use of the same. Even transporters are now heavily making use of Paytm for making various payments while they are on road(toll payments).

Dabur's View on Impact of Demonetization on FMCG

"Demonetization of high value currency note initiated by the government is a positive move for the economy and industry and will lead to better transparency and compliance in the medium to long run. This will be beneficial for organised FMCG players creating a level playing field," Dabur Ltd said a regulatory filing. Elaborating on the impact, the company said it will vary across channels and geographies and stress is highest for wholesalers and small town grocery shops, who are facing a severe liquidity crisis and are destocking.

"The impact is likely to be positive on modern trade outlets and plastic enabled retailers who are likely to benefit from this change," it said. However, on account of continuity of current uncertain situation it is difficult to quantify the impact for third quarter on the company at this point in time, Dabur said. "However, it is temporary in nature and situation will improve with increase in availability of new currency. In the meanwhile, we are focussing more on modern retail, e-commerce and institutional sales and also encouraging our general trade (GT) retailers to adopt cashless payment systems," it added.

This will help in mitigating the overall impact of demonetization and pave the way for normalisation in the next few months, the company said.

Conclusion: FMCG sector to recover fully from demonetization effect in this fiscal year. In spite of all the flaws in the entire process of demonetization and various problems faced by the entire country, recovery is expected at the earliest. Life is getting back to normal with change in withdrawals from ATMs per day, shorter queues at the ATMs, less pressure on the bankers, increased amount of cash in hand, people equipping to use digital methods of payments etc. As a positive effect of demonetization, there is a move towards formal economy and organised national players. It might be challenging for the regional players who are largely unorganized in nature. Sooner we adopt to varied means of transactions easier it will be to evade losses.

The markets will now be more clean and transparent as there will be lesser chances of evading indirect taxes, thus lowering the possibility of black-money floating in.

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